

Affordances of intimacy. An ecological approach to human-product interaction

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Abstract In this paper, I propose the possibility of adopting an ecological approach and the concept of affordance to analyze the phenomenon of human-product interaction as a whole, thus considering not only instrumental interactions, but also non-instrumental and non-physical ones (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). I claim that the concept of affordance has been interpreted narrowly so far, while it could be applied, to some extent, also to the affective realm, and thus to understand not only relationships of physical proximity but also of psychological intimacy. The aim is to identify key factors in the establishment of intimate relationships, in order to understand how the experience of intimacy can be linked to product properties. The topic of intimate relationships with objects is relevant in the field of design especially because it favors the acceptance of objects and technologies at various levels of intimacy: from the domestic sphere to portable devices, wearable technologies, and prosthesis.

Keywords *Affordances, Intimacy, Human-product interaction, Ecological approach, Expressive qualities*

The concept of intimacy

That of intimacy is an intuitive concept used to describe many different things, like people (i.e. an intimate person may be a relative, a close friend or a partner), objects (i.e. things in close relation with our bodies, like clothes and other belongings), or places (e.g. our home). With the concept of intimacy we can refer both to physical proximity and to psychological closeness. Why do we use the same word for such different things? Is it just a metaphor or is there anything in common among these things? What are the characteristics that give rise to this kind experience?

In everyday language, for example, we use the adjective “intimate” to describe a place which is private, cozy, warm, familiar, and makes us feel relaxed and comfortable, but, if we had to design an intimate place, what characteristics should we focus on? What design factors are involved?

A concept similar to that of intimacy, which moreover constitutes a nearly synonymous, is that of warmth.

Several studies in social psychology (Williams and Bargh, 2008; IJzerman and Semin, 2010; Fiske, Cuddy and Glick, 2007) have shown similarities and connections among behavioral effects generated by physical warmth (the temperature of an object or of an environment) and those arising from the experience of psychological warmth (originated by characteristics like color, material, form, etc.).

Other insights from social psychology lead us to a definition of intimacy, that, despite developed with reference to interpersonal relationships, can be applied to study human-product interaction.

In social psychology, the concept of intimacy is closely linked to that of privacy, which refers to the mechanism of regulation of exchanges that take place between the self and the outside world, and thus can be defined as “a boundary control process” (Pedersen, 1997). Indeed, intimacy can be seen as a specific level of privacy (Westin, 1968; Pedersen, 1997), in which the most relevant boundary is not the one referring to the person’s self, but the one enclosing a small group. The members of this group reduce contact with outsiders while increasing interactions between them. They share private information and develop joint projects and goals, in a relationship of interdependence.

As a consequence, the main feature of an intimate relationship is the gradual shift in perspective from one of “me and you” to one of “us”. This determines the emergence of a new system with its own unique properties, based on the presence of interpersonal premises and expectations (Chelune, Robison and Kommor, 1984). Indeed, according to Chelune, Robison and Kommor, “intimacy is a relational property. It does not lie within a person or in a situation, but emerges out of their interaction. It is a characteristic of a system, which influences and is influenced by its components” (Chelune, Robison and Kommor, 1984, p. 25).

An ecological approach to intimate relationships

If intimacy is a relational property emerging out of interaction, it can be addressed through an ecological approach. This perspective, as described by Gibson (1979), is based on the principle of mutuality of animal and environment, according to which, the individual and the environment are not to be regarded as separate entities, but as parts of a whole system. Thus,

in order to understand how a certain animal lives, we have to consider its integration in its own ecological niche, which means to conceive the characteristics of the animal and that of its environment relationally. Building on this assumption, Gibson describes the ecological niche as a set of affordances, that are action possibilities emerging from the union between person-related and environment-related aspects that are structurally proportionate.

Given that the environment provides multiple affordances, what determines the type of interaction that will occur is the ubiquitous and continuous process of selection that an individual has to implement (Withagen, de Poel, Araújo and Pepping, 2012). The appraisal of the opportunities provided by the environment, which is fundamental to understand the link between the affordances as action possibilities and the actual actions, is also at the basis of the act of approaching. Indeed, according to Gibson, the distances we keep are important for maintaining our safety and also to “obtain beneficial encounters” (Gibson, 1979, p. 232), and, in order to comprehend the kind of distance that should be maintained, the individual must be able to distinguish a positive affordance from a negative one. Thus, relationships of proximity are based on the perception of positive affordances, which springs out from an appraisal of the relevance of an external resource in relation to the person’s concerns.

Another key principle of the theory of affordances, which is important to keep in mind, is that the perceiver should be considered as a whole, hence rejecting the dichotomy between body and mind and conceiving perception as “a psychosomatic act” (Gibson, 1979, p. 240). This principle leads us to understand that a positive affordance can be determined not only by the functional value of an object, but also by other object’s values. I claim that, as Overbeeke and Wensveen highlight, “if affordances are about meaning, they are not just about functional meaning; they do not only fit our perceptual-motor skills, but also our emotional and cognitive skills. Man as a whole should be respectfully embraced” (Overbeeke and Wensveen, 2003, pp. 93-94).

The establishment of an intimate relationship, on the basis of the functional value of an object, can be observed in the case of the interaction with tools. As Gibson claims, “when in use, a tool is a sort of extension of the hand, almost an attachment to it or a part of the user’s own body, and thus is no longer a part of the environment of the user” (Gibson, 1979, p. 41).

In a similar way, relationships of intimacy can be established through the union between expressive meanings and psychological capabilities. In a recent study on music perception, based on the ecological approach, Krueger claims that music is a structured sound-time phenomenon with an instrumental value: it affords movement through emotion regulation. Moreover, he states that in everyday life we perceive music “as a resource we can use to do different things, much the same way we perceive tools and technologies

as resources that help us accomplish different tasks”, and that “we potentially use music to become part of an integrated brain–body–music system” (Krueger, 2013 pp. 1-2).

In “The ecological approach to visual perception”, Gibson takes into account this kind of meanings addressing them as “subtle invariants”, and gives us a significant example describing the act of kissing someone: “to kiss someone, magnify the face-form, if the facial expression is amiable, so as almost to fill the field of view” (Gibson, 1979, p. 233). So we can think to the expressive structure of the face as the bearer of a meaning that corresponds to an action possibility (amiable expression = positive affordance = approach allowed).

Gibson clarifies this point claiming that “the value is clear on the face of it, as we say, and thus it has a physiognomic quality in the way that the emotions of a man appear on his face” (Gibson, 1979, p. 138). With Gibson’s reference to physiognomic qualities, the role of Gestalt psychology in the formulation of the theory of affordances becomes clear. Indeed a positive affordance has the same attractive value of the concepts of “demand character” and “invitation character” or “valence”, developed respectively by Koffka (1935) and Lewin (1935).

Finally, we must remember that, as shown by experimental studies of Michotte on causality (1950), and Heider e Simmel on interpersonal perception (1944), the recognition of physiognomic qualities does not happen only in the case of the interaction between people or between animals, but also in the observation of inanimate objects.

Design factors for intimate relationships

In a very similar vein, the above mentioned issues can be found in recent design studies on intimacy.

Bell et al. (2003), talking about ubiquitous computing, identify three possible forms of intimacy: “1. Intimacy as cognitive and emotional closeness with technology, where the technology (typically unidirectionally) may be aware of, and responsive to, our intentions, actions and feelings. Here our technologies know us intimately; we may or may not know them intimately. 2. Intimacy as physical closeness with technology, both on the body and/or within the body. 3. Intimacy through technology: technology that can express of our intentions, actions and feelings toward others” (Bell, Brooke, Churchill and Paulos, 2003, p. 2). Each case highlights different aspects to focus on, when designing artifacts. In the first case, the main issue is that of privacy, which may be violated in terms of personal informations, so boundaries protection (both virtual or material boundaries) should be under attention. In the second case, the main issue is that of technology acceptance in physical personal space, so designers should focus on sensitive characteristics like temperature, material, weight, interaction patterns, etc. In the latter case the object acts as a medium, through which people establish or maintain interpersonal relationships, so the design of the artifact should be focused on aesthetic appearance, or

on communication channels it enables and boundaries protection, if we refer to communication softwares that mediate intimacy.

Other aspects have been highlighted by experimental studies in Human Robot Interaction, that observed the rise of strong engagements between people and domestic robots, such as entertainment, nursing and service robots (Sung, Guo, Grinter and Christensen, 2007; Friedman, Kahn and Hagman, 2003; Marti, Pollini, Rullo and Shibata, 2005). Many of these works have found that people tend to ascribe human qualities to robots such as name, gender, ethnicity, personality, and even cognitive or emotional states, interpreting their behavior as if they were governed by rational choices and desires. The attribution of anthropomorphic or zoomorphic features may engage people and robots “in a humanlike interaction, which implies politeness, reciprocity and self-disclosure” (Scopelliti, Giuliani and Fornara, 2005), thus favoring intimate relationships. Considering the studies in experimental psychology previously observed, the recognition of these qualities in inanimate objects could be due to movement, behaviors and interaction patterns.

Conclusions

Through the theoretical contribution of social psychology, a definition of intimacy has been identified. This definition has been reframed through an ecological approach, in order to highlight the key factors characterizing intimate relationships, understood both as physical closeness and as psychological intimacy.

According to the ecological approach, on the one hand, relationships of physical closeness with objects can be established through functional affordances, on the other hand, relationships of psychological intimacy depend on other “subtle invariants” or expressive qualities. The process of appraisal and the concept of valence are fundamental in both physical and psychological intimacy. In this we can find a link with emotion theory.

Design studies in ubiquitous computing and human-robot interaction confirm these findings, and allow us to understand how some key factors, like boundaries and expressive qualities, can inform the design of artifacts.

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